

THE POSITION OF SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGY IN THE WORLD TODAY

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Abstract: This article provides information on the history of the development of Social Psychology, its functions as a scientific science of Social Psychology and the current significance of Social Psychology. One thing is worth noting that in the current period of development, the study of social psychology remains a topical issue, so we recommend to study this science with diligence.

Key words: Social Psychology, small groups and Communities, Social Psychological Study of an individual, reciprocity.

In the IX session of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan the Republican first President I.A. Karimov focused on public attention that there is a special role in the training of higher education and qualifying personnel. Indeed, the person should only increase the slight talent, knowledge and level of knowledge, but also will be ready for a different social relations system in society, the scientific laws and regulations of social activities. In areas of management, marketing and management. The knowledge of the human factor and the psychological system of its management is a means of development of a healthy human relationship in society through the formation of healthy humanitarian relations. Therefore, as far as the head of state is to analyze the most effective methods of management of all spiritual, mental and humanistic relations engaged in the education of a harmoniously. The study of the mechanisms of improving the mechanisms of social thinking, especially the social thinking, new worldview and relations, is one of the most pressing issues. According to Russian scientist G.M.Andreeva, who is actually reflected in the field of social psychology, because it

is a sociologist, the traditions of social laws are before And if you seek to explain in the language of general rules, the psychologist is trying to apply the laws of the specific derived psychology in general law. Therefore, G.ANDEEEVA Bases three different approaches about the topic discussion of social psychology, based on the fact that sociological, psychological and sociological and psychological. In any case, the scientific sources, which lead to a separate science of social psychology, to resolve the achievements of psychology and sociological sciences and any of certain problems in any matter The fact that the additional science must have the need to have a separate science is a set of people. His progress and spiritual potential depend on the nature of the relationship between these people, the content of the complex social partnerships they are implementing. As long as everyone lives in society, it seeks to be a special place and independent position in it, so it demonstrates unique pursuit, samples of activity. There are a number of social sciences between people and a number of social sciences studying the relationship between the nature and nature of its various social relations, and the social psychology has a special place.

Based on the tasks of social psychology, the following groups may be divided into areas or objects that cover the topic of the debate. Psychology of small groups and communities. The dynamic processes that take part in this area and the psychological structure of small groups (Organizational, mutuality, and so on the psychological structure of small groups (Organizational, mutuality, etc.) to research objects in this area. Psychology of leadership and management of leadership in groups; incident of conformation; Terms of formation of teams, various groups of inter-group relations. In intimacy of mutual communication among the people in groups is an important task of social psychology of groups, both in groups. The society is a set of people. His development and logal are in connection with the nature of mutual relations between these people, the complex social partnerships they carry out. As long as everyone lives in society, it seeks to be a small place and independent position in it, and so it demonstrates mealful aspirations, adaptation and activity. There are a number of social issues between people and the role of the place of human people and the nature of its various social relations, including a special place. It enters. Social processes depend on

the period for the period, which is directly related to the changes involving changes in society. Therefore, the famous French scientist, the Serly French scientist wrote: "Social psychology has set the responsibility of society directly."

Conclusion: In conclusion, we can say that our body as one of the subjects with a very gradual subjects. This means that the tasks of social psychology, the problems of social psychology, are directly stemmed from society. The tasks of our republics are independently have been independently, and the tasks of our society are to be solved at the time of socially psychological changes in our society. It is prove that there is less an important risk of social psychology today. This means that in the context of production and in the context of the new market economy, they change their thinking, their imaginations, and the peculiarity of the identity of a person is that these science people are one - From what they think of one is a science that will learn how to influence each other.

Refereencies:

1. S.R. Kamolova "Social psychology" Tashkent - 2015.
2. N.Ismoilova, D.Abdullayeva “Ijtimoiy psixologiya” Toshkent – 2013.
3. Sh.Sh.Hafizov “Ijtimoiy psixologiya” o’quv qo’llanma Buxoro – 2008.
4. Алдер Г. IQ или мускулы творческого интеллекта. Пер. с англ. С. Потапенко. - М: ФАИР-ПРЕСС, 2004.
5. Зимняя И.А. Педагогическая психология: Учебник для вузов. Изд. второе, доп., испр. и перераб. — М.: Логос, 2002.
6. Karimova V.M., Sunnatova R.I., Tojibayeva R.N. Mustaqil fikrlash. - T.: Sharq. 2000.
7. Абрамова Г.С. Возрастная психология. - М: Академия, 1999.
8. Ibrohimjon M. et al. PSYCHOLOGICAL CRISES IN PERSONALITY PSYCHOLOGY AND WAYS TO OVERCOME THEM // Galaxy international interdisciplinary Research Journal. 2022. –Т. 10. – N 4. – С . 743-746